

FOLKLORE IN UZBEK LITERATURE

Hamdamova Mohidilxon To'xtasinovna

A teacher of School № 24 Kokand, Uzbekistan

Email: malikarajapova1993@gmail.com

Contact number: +998912054169

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ANNOTATION

Uzbek literature is well known all around the world and it is very crucial to save the traditions of Uzbek nation. Moreover, literature plays a crucial role in bringing up children. A potential part of literature is folklore since it shows the whole nation and the people's intelligence. The following article describes the importance of Uzbek literature and some subgroups of it. Also, it shows some developing steps of the literature.

Key words: literature, world literature, folklore, lullaby, doston.

Folklore plays a significant role in Uzbek literature, reflecting the rich cultural and historical heritage of Uzbekistan. Uzbek folklore is a treasure trove of oral traditions, including legends, fairy tales, epic poems, and proverbs that date back centuries. These stories and sayings have been passed down through generations, serving not only as entertainment but also as a means of preserving the history, values, and beliefs of the Uzbek people.

Epic Tales and Heroic Poems

One of the most famous examples of Uzbek folklore is the epic tale of "Alpamysh," which is central to the Turkic oral literature tradition. "Alpamysh" is a heroic epic poem that embodies the ideals of honor, bravery, and love. It tells the story of Alpamysh's quest to win back his beloved Barchin, overcoming numerous trials and challenges. The epic highlights themes of loyalty, the struggle against injustice, and the pursuit of freedom, which resonate with the Uzbek spirit.

Fairy Tales and Folk Stories

Uzbek fairy tales and folk stories often feature magical creatures, talking animals, and fantastical events. These stories teach moral lessons, impart wisdom, and explore themes such as kindness, cleverness, and the triumph of good over evil. Characters like wise elders, cunning foxes, and brave young heroes are common, reflecting the values and social norms of Uzbek society.

Proverbs and Sayings

Uzbek proverbs and sayings are another integral part of the country's folklore, encapsulating the wisdom and philosophy of the Uzbek people. These short, expressive phrases cover various aspects of life, including family,

friendship, work, and ethics. They are often used in daily conversation, serving as a guide for behavior and decision-making.

Influence on Uzbek Literature

Folklore has profoundly influenced Uzbek literature, inspiring poets, writers, and playwrights. The themes, characters, and motifs found in traditional folklore have been woven into modern literary works, creating a unique blend of the old and the new. This fusion enriches Uzbek literature, making it a vibrant and dynamic reflection of the nation's heritage and contemporary life.

Preservation and Revival

Efforts are being made to preserve and revive Uzbek folklore as a vital part of the country's cultural legacy. Initiatives include collecting and documenting folk tales, epic poems, and proverbs, as well as incorporating folklore into educational curricula. Cultural festivals, performances, and competitions also play a significant role in keeping the rich tradition of Uzbek folklore alive for future generations.

Folklore in Uzbek literature, as in many cultures, has evolved through various stages, reflecting changes in society, politics, and the cultural landscape. The development of Uzbek folklore can be broadly categorized into several key stages, from ancient times to the modern era. Here's an overview of these stages:

Pre-Islamic Period

Ancient Myths and Legends: This period includes the earliest forms of folklore, which were oral traditions encompassing myths, legends, and epic tales. These stories often featured heroes, gods, and mythical creatures, reflecting the beliefs and values of ancient Central Asian societies.

Islamic Influence

Adoption and Adaptation: With the introduction of Islam around the 8th century, Uzbek folklore began to incorporate Islamic themes, characters, and moral lessons. However, many pre-Islamic elements were preserved, leading to a rich blend of cultural narratives.

Literary Flourishing: The Timurid Renaissance (14th-15th centuries) marked a significant period of cultural and literary development in Central Asia. During this time, folklore began to be recorded in writing, alongside the creation of new works influenced by Islamic literature.

Russian and Soviet Influence

Colonial Impact: The Russian Empire's expansion into Central Asia in the 19th century brought new influences on Uzbek folklore, introducing European literary forms and ideas, which were sometimes blended with local traditions.

Soviet Era: Under Soviet rule (20th century), folklore was both promoted as a form of national culture and controlled to align with socialist ideals. Traditional tales were often adapted to include themes of class struggle and socialism, and folkloric research was institutionalized.

Modern Period

Revival and Preservation: Following Uzbekistan's independence in 1991, there has been a resurgence of interest in traditional Uzbek folklore, with efforts to preserve and revitalize this cultural heritage. This includes scholarly research, collections of folk tales, and the integration of folklore into education.

Contemporary Adaptations: Modern Uzbek writers and artists continue to draw on folklore, using traditional themes and motifs to address contemporary issues and to explore Uzbek identity in a globalized world.

Each of these stages reflects broader socio-political changes and has contributed to the richness of Uzbek folklore, making it a vital component of Uzbek literature and cultural identity. The evolution of folklore in Uzbek literature demonstrates the dynamic interplay between tradition and innovation, local identity, and external influences.

In summary, folklore is an essential component of Uzbek literature, representing the heart and soul of Uzbek culture. Through its epic tales, fairy tales, and proverbs, Uzbek folklore continues to inspire, educate, and entertain, connecting the past with the present and future

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